

Prevalence, Knowledge, Perceptions, Attitudes, and Role of Traditional Healers in Snake Bites and Envenomations in the Bofidji-Ouest Group, Democratic Republic of the Congo¹

Blaise Engomba Mokekola

Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences, Higher Pedagogical Institute of Mbandaka, Mbandaka,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, National Pedagogical University, Kinshasa, Democratic
Republic of the Congo
blaisemok4@gmail.com

Koto-Te-Nyiwa Ngbolua

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Center for Research in Pharmacopoeia and Traditional Medicine, Higher Institute of Medical
Techniques, Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo

Idrissa Assumani Zabo

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, National Pedagogical University, Kinshasa, Democratic
Republic of the Congo
idrissa.assumani@upn.ac.cd

Guy Bayeli Ilumbe

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo
guy_ilumbe@yahoo.com

Aristarque Mulonda

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, National Pedagogical University, Kinshasa, Democratic
Republic of the Congo
aristarque.mulonda@upn.ac.cd

Monizi Mawunu

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

¹Address Author Correspondence to Koto-Te-Nyiwa Ngbolua at jpngbolua@unikin.ac.cd
Accepted: 29 October 2024 / Published online: 04 November 2024
© The Author(s), 2024. Paper ID, 100330.

Department of Agronomy & Botanical Garden of the Polytechnic Institute of the University Kimpa Vita,
Angola

m.mawunu2000@gmail.com

Giresse Engomba

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

giresengomba@gmail.com

Colette Ashande Masengo

Center for Research in Pharmacopoeia and Traditional Medicine, Higher Institute of Medical
Techniques, Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo

Medical Biology Section, Higher Institute of Medical Techniques, Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of
the Congo

masengocolette@gmail.com

Godefroid Libono Ekamba

Office for the Biodiversity of Bomongo, REDD+ Independent researcher, Province of Equator,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

godefroidekamba01@gmail.com

Abstract

The pathology of bites and envenomations poses significant public health, social, economic, and environmental challenges in Bofidji, West DRC. In the absence of modern health infrastructure and serotherapy, traditional medicine remains the primary means of intervention for snakebite envenomation, a serious medical and surgical emergency. This study incorporates an epidemiological survey of snakebite incidents alongside an ethnobotanical survey, examining local plants and traditional treatments, and the knowledge of practitioners in managing these emergencies. Data was collected retrospectively in 2019 and 2020 to assess the frequency of bites by season, gender, and demographic factors, with a specific focus on variations among women. The results identified 33 plants used in local ethnobotany for treating snakebites, alongside various animal extracts utilized in medicinal preparations. Statistical analyses revealed significant patterns in snakebite incidence related to socio-demographic variables. The study highlights the gendered perspectives and cultural practices surrounding treatment methods and knowledge sharing among local healers. While there is openness among healthcare practitioners to integrate traditional methods into modern protocols, barriers persist, including cultural differences and the need for scientific validation of traditional knowledge. This study underscores the importance of local expertise in managing envenomations and advocates for a holistic healthcare approach that bridges traditional and modern medicine. Such integration presents challenges but offers a pathway for more

inclusive and culturally sensitive healthcare practices, ultimately aiming to improve patient outcomes in the management of snakebite incidents.

Keywords

Cultural Practices, Traditional Medicine, Community Health, Medicinal Plants, Public Health.

1. Introduction-

Snakebites are a real social, economic and public health problem worldwide, especially for rural populations in developing countries (Chippaux, 1998 ; Barma et al., 2014; Upasani et al., 2017; Ayékotchami & Adandé, 2021). Ophidian envenomation is also a medical-surgical emergency that is poorly addressed by health services in most tropical countries (Falçal et al. 2016). It is reported in the literature that approximately 500,000 to five million people worldwide are victims of ophidian envenomation every year (Falçal et al., 2016; Ngbolua 2021; Mokekola et al., 2022a,b, 2024a; 2024b). Of these victims, 10% die and around 400,000 are left with serious after-effects (Aubert, De Haro & Jouglard, 1996; Ngbolua et al., 2021). Elapidae and Viperidae are the two most frequently incriminated families of venomous snakes (Gentilini, 1993; Ngbolua et al., 2021). In Africa, bites are associated with farming, hunting or walking (Bellefleur & Le Dantec, 2005).

In many tropical countries, people are unlikely to have access to modern medicine. Indeed, the lack of health infrastructure, the constant increase in the price of health products and services, and the inaccessibility of generic medicines are major problems for financially disadvantaged populations (Ngene et al., 2015). Sometimes, even when patients have the means to purchase imported medicines, there is virtually no infrastructure to transport these medicines (Balagizi, 2010) to the most remote areas, in addition to the non-existence of antivenom serotherapy centres (Chippaux, 2005; Ngbolua et al., 2021). Presumably due to cultural and financial constraints (Mokekola et al., 2024a,b), the majority of victims resort only to traditional medicine.

The African flora constitutes an important reserve of medicinal plants that occupy an important place in the African pharmacopoeia (Inkoto et al., 2021a; Masengo et al., 2021; Ngunde et al., 2021). Today, they still play a crucial role in the treatment of certain tropical diseases (Inkoto et al., 2021b). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 80% of the population in Africa in general, and in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) in particular, use traditional medicine for primary health care (Kabena et al., 2014). The use of medicinal plants for various health problems is not only a choice, but is also reportedly linked to poverty and the high costs of modern medicines (Ngbolua et al., 2016; Masunda et al., 2019). This reliance on plants is also justified by a strong attachment to traditional know-how and the availability of plant material through a large Congolese rainforest, comprising just over 10,000 species of angiosperms, of which approximately 3,000 are endemic (ATIBT, 2006).

However, Kouame (2018) notes that African Traditional Medicine (TM) is seen as a complementary health system to Modern Medicine (MM). It has the advantage of being easier to access, less costly and more adapted to local specificities. Kouame (2018) also notes the lack of sharing and conservation

of medical knowledge in TM: the majority of TM Practitioners (PMT) speak uncodified local languages, and many keep their knowledge secret. Collaboration between health practitioners and participants faces a number of unfortunately undocumented barriers and challenges. The transmission of knowledge is not formalized, either within the lineage or among members attached to the responsible traditherapist.

In any case, traditional medicine continues to be a significant resource (Carillon, 2009 ; Kouame, 2018) for conventional medicine, particularly Modern Medicine (MM). In a rural environment lacking well-equipped health structures, it would be desirable to explore the diversity of problems that stand in the way of the ultimate integration of inter-ethnic traditional medicine (traditional herbal medicine) on the one hand, and modern herbal medicine (clinical herbal medicine) on the other, through a pooling of the local knowledge held by gender.

Traditional phytotherapy is an ancient practice based on the use of plants according to their empirically discovered virtues. Traditional herbal medicine is considered a TM and is still widely used in developing countries, according to the WHO (Sowa, 2013). It is a non-conventional medicine due to the absence of clinical and scientific studies. Conventional medicine is taught according to a detailed curriculum. It is based on scientific advances in the search for active plant extracts or drugs (Chabrier, 2010; Sowa, 2013). In traditional medicine, the curriculum does not follow the same requirements. In the Bofidji - Ouest grouping, female tradiphytotherapists are very much in evidence, playing a major role in the traditional health system alongside male tradiphytotherapists. This influence calls for a deeper understanding of the roles, levels of knowledge, practices, methods and collaboration between male and female tradipraticians, as both have different heritages depending on their gender. Presumably, there are challenges and barriers that isolate traditional medicine from conventional medicine that need to be elucidated in order to channel its integration into modern healthcare practices.

The work of Atemezing, Fotso, Tchotsoua & Cardon (2009) and Atemezing & Juan (2009) focuses on the validation of TM knowledge managed by an agent system. The author discusses the concepts of ritual, traditional health care practices (diagnosis, divination, and religious belief), witchcraft, patient, potion, disease, and symptom and so on.

In Cameroon, Ayimdji, Koussoube, Fotso & Balira (2012), Baader & Hollunder (1991), have produced ontology on TM with Methontology. They described the process of collecting a plant through the collector (his sex, young or old, his behavioral attitude including the fact that no breaks are allowed during this collection of the plant, then after collection, the plant is directly transported home to be used on the patient). The timing of the collection is also important.

These and other works, dealing with ethnomedicinal aspects and various traditional practices, hardly speak of gender. Both men and women have inherited popular and specific knowledge from parents who felt that they were entrusting this or that person with secret matters concerning the metaphysical power inspired by invisible beings. Such TM practices may be superficial in the female or male practitioner, or anchored or reductionist over time, far from revealing the holistic aspect of a patient's treatment. This can often have a negative impact on the treatment of bites and envenomations, the risk of which is unfortunately great for young children (Mokekola et al., 2022c).

Furthermore, El Hattimyr (2015) has shown that children under 15 years of age are 2.58 times more likely to die from an envenomation than adults. We know that the majority of the population in terms of age groups in rural areas of the DRC is made up of children in this category; paradoxically, it is also the most vulnerable class in the Bofidji - Ouest group, which is our physical study setting. In the neighbouring groupement of Bonginda, several children have died from bites and envenomations, as reported by (Mokekola et al., 2022a).

In 2009, the DRC Ministry of Health published the first edition of the DRC Traditional Pharmacopoeia. Konda ku Mbuta et al. (2011) published "Plantes médicinales de traditions Province de l'Equateur - R.D. Congo". Certainly, medicinal plants are a fundamental, readily available and easily accessible component of local community health systems for a wide range of ailments, including envenomations of animal origin, in this case snake (Soares et al., 2005). These plants are a rich source of natural inhibitors and pharmacologically active compounds (Amui, Puga, Soares & Ginlia, 2011; Ayimdji, Koussoube, Fotso & Balira, 2021). A large number of ethnobotanical studies have reported the snake venom-neutralising properties of several medicinal plants (Gomes et al., 2010; Felix-Silva et al., 2017). Generally speaking, in developing countries (Mokekola et al., 2022a, c) such as DR Congo, and particularly in the rural areas of Equateur province where the risk of envenoming accidents is major given the particular geographical situation that characterizes it, the health infrastructure, the availability of medicines and staff training are insufficient to meet an otherwise poorly specified health demand. It is therefore essential (Pagezy, 2006) to improve our knowledge of the epidemiology of snakebites in order to better organize their management (Kassogue, 2006 ; Ngbolua et al., 2021) in real time and in any location.

The implementation of a healthcare offer adapted to local conditions, combined with ongoing training of healthcare personnel in various health zones and mass campaigns through families in rural areas, should significantly reduce a mortality rate that remains unacceptable given the effectiveness of current anti-venom immunoglobulins (Diarra, 2005; Dramé, 2000; Fourn, Adè, Fayomi & Zohoun, 2005) in circulation in developed countries on the one hand, and the use of endogenous knowledge benefiting from the enormous floristic and zoological resources naturally available in almost all rural environments on the other.

The present surveys envisaged in Bofidji - West will enable us to grasp the scope of the incidences of snakebite and envenomations on the one hand, and also to assess and compare the level of knowledge of anti-snakebite medicinal plants between traditional and traditional health therapists in the region.

The main objective of this study was to inventory the therapeutic (medicinal) resources used in the treatment of snakebite and envenomation, and to assess and compare the level of knowledge as well as gender dynamics (female and male tradipraticians) practicing traditional medicine in Bofidji - West.

The specific objectives were to :

- Assess the ethnobotanical value of the various plants surveyed
- Assess the knowledge and practices of traditional health practitioners in the management of bites and envenomations, with a focus on gender differences (female and male traditional practitioners).

- Explore gender dynamics in the transmission of knowledge and practice of traditional health care related to snakebites and envenomations, and gender interactions in the transmission of knowledge and practice of traditional health care related to snakebites and envenomations.

- To examine potential challenges and barriers in the vision of integrating traditional phytomedicine into modern health structures and partnering with international health NGOs based in Equateur Province. Our research will provide valuable information on traditional health methods in Bofidji - West, as well as on gender interactions and their influence on the management of bites and envenomations. The results will deepen our understanding of local traditional medicinal practices in and around Bofidji-West. This will facilitate more effective and better-informed health interventions in the region, to the benefit of the possible integration of traditional medicine into conventional health structures. Intercultural dialogue and collaboration between traditional and modern medicine could also be supported by the results of this study, by identifying the strengths and limitations of different approaches often used by tradiphytotherapists.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study setting

The Bofidji - Ouest Groupement is in the Bikoro Territory. Highly vulnerable (Boika et al., 2021), it is under the climatic influence of Lake Tumba, which is bathed in a humid tropical equatorial climate characterized by almost constant temperatures, low variations in temperature and abundant, regular rainfall (Mokekola et al., 2022a,b). The Bofidji-Ouest cluster, our study setting, with geographical coordinates, is a community located in a rural region characterized by significant biodiversity, including various species of snakes and other venomous animals. The region is characterized by deep-rooted traditional health practices, with variable access to modern healthcare. Environmental and cultural conditions in Bofidji - West

The main ethnic groups (Bayeli et al., 2019; Pagezy, 2006) are the Ntomba, Ekonda, Ngele'a'ntando (Bantu) and Twa (indigenous pygmy population). These ethnic groups are made up of farmers, fishermen, traders and advanced people (state officials or employers in other organizations). The way of life is somewhat different between all these ethnic groups (Bantu) and the indigenous population, which could explain certain heterogeneity in the population.

a. Sampling

The pre-surveys enabled us to identify male and female tradiphytotherapists, male and female herbalists (a total of 25 subjects, including 9 women and 16 men) and other people among the victims of bites and envenomations, including people who had been at the bedside of patients during 2019 and 2020 in the selected sites (113 subjects in all) for the surveys proper.

01 Graph associated with data table 1 : Survey population age groups

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 1 shows the age distribution of the study population. It also shows the age structure of the subjects surveyed, as well as the representativeness of the participants. It can be seen that among the subjects who took part in the survey, the age group of more or less ten years was not involved. The most representative age group is between 31 and 40.

02 Graph associated with data table 2 : Professional status of respondents

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 2. This table shows the jobs and frequencies of the survey participants. This diversity certainly provides varied information for the benefit of the survey in terms of risk factors and recovery or mortality rates, as well as the resources used for care. The sample was dominated by housewives and farmers, who tied at 13.04%. Unemployed people (9.42%) and lumberjacks (8.69%) make up a very important group who took part in the survey.

03 Graph associated with data table 3 : Marital status of respondents

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 3 : This table provides information on the marital

status of the subjects who took part in the surveys. The figures show the different marital status of the respondents who took part in the surveys. The sample is dominated by single women (21.74%), followed by single men (17.39%). Married men are the least represented.

04 Graph associated with data table 4 : Status of respondents by gender

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 4 : The table on the status of respondents by gender shows which men and which women are more likely to respond to surveys, and to be more open to community issues in general, and to ethnomedical surveys in particular. Women predominate at 59.42%, while men account for 40.58%.

Utilisation of R

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

p-value = 0.6402

The P-value (= 0,6402) is less or greater than 0.005, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant association between seasons and sex of bitten persons

05 Graph associated with data table 5 : Distribution of respondents by ethnic Group in Groupement Bofidji – Ouest

The Graph associated with data table 5 above shows the number of respondents according to the indigenous ethnic groups that make up the Bofidji - Ouest Groupement. In addition to the figures presented by ethnic groups, there is a clear willingness among respondents to contribute significantly

to explaining and defending their cultural practices. The survey includes two castes: the Oto, with 91 respondents (65.94%), and the Twa, with 47 respondents (34.06%).

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

The P-value (= 0,789) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant association between seasons and sex of bitten persons

b. Data collection

The nature of the retrospective study required the administration of an oral questionnaire to those involved in the survey. Data were collected using the standardized interview method. The individual interview technique was preferred. The oral questionnaire was drawn up in French and translated into the local dialect, depending on whether the respondent was TWA or OTO.

Data collection took ethical considerations into account. It focused on ethnographic data and data from the inventory of samples of medicinal plants used to treat bites and envenomations, as well as data on gender aspects, their implications in the ethnophytotherapy of bite and envenomations and the available potential reflected by gender for an integration to be federated towards effective collaboration with the modern health structures based in Bofidji. But also towards a pooling of endogenous knowledge for an enriched (strengthened) traditional medicine that can thus contribute to a better understanding and informed recommendations for improving health care in this region.

c. Data analysis

The data collected were analyzed through the following ethnobotanical parameters:

❖ **Citation Frequency (CF)**

A technique that takes into account the consensus of participants can be used to assess the cultural significance of plants. The level of knowledge of medicinal plants was assessed by the Citation Frequency (CF). The FC is the number of times that respondents mentioned a given plant species to treat the pathology targeted by the study. It is a good index to assess the credibility of the information received and the level of knowledge of plants within a population ([Mokekola et al. 2022a](#), [Mokekola et al. 2024b](#)).

$$FC = \frac{F_c}{N}$$

where

- CF: Citation Frequency
- Fc: Number of respondents who mentioned the species in the treatment of hepatitis;
- N: Total number of respondents.

❖ **Use Value (VU)**

The VU makes it possible to determine the species having a high use value in a given environment. It has been used to establish a hierarchy of importance at the species level according to the formula used by ([Camou-Guerrero et al. 2022](#) ; [Ngbolua KN, et al. 2019](#); [Mokekola et al. 2022a](#) ; [Mokekola et al. 2024b](#)).

$$VU = \frac{\sum Si}{n}$$

where

- VU : Use Value of a given species.
- Si : Usage score assigned by respondent i
- n : number of respondents for the given category of use

2.3.3 Interpretation

- If $1 < VU < 1.50$: the species has a low use value, therefore it is less threatened with extinction;
- If $VU = 1.50$: the species has an average use value;
- If $1.50 < VU < 03$: the species is at risk of extinction following excessive exploitation. The study emphasised the importance of ethnobotanical Use Value (**EV**) as a tool for selecting the most sought-after plants (preferred species). At the end of the surveys, an importance score was given to each species by the respondent. The assessment grid used is: 3 (highly sought-after species), 2 (moderately sought-after species) and 1 (weakly sought-after species). The calculated **VU** made it possible to identify the number of preferred species that fit into different recipes used for the phytotherapy of the bite. The information thus obtained was used to calculate the ethnobotanical use value of the plants. (Lougbeignon et al. (2015) ; Engomba et al. 2022 ; Mokekola et al. 2024a). The **EV** was used to identify species with a high use value in the study area. It was used to establish a hierarchy of importance at the species level according to the formula used by Lougbeignon et al. (2015).

For some tables, we used Excel to analyze the data. This was the case with the socio-demographic data, ethnobotanical inventory, ethnotradiophytherapeutic knowledge and integration of traditional medicine which were translated into graphs. Data have been presented using Excel 2016. Graphs have been produced using Excel 2016. The chart format was combined with the data table. Some data tables have been subjected to the Ki-square test or Fisher test for statistical interpretation should this prove important.

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Helsinki Protocol (World Medical Association, 2013) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (United Nations, 1992).

3. Results

3.1. Inventory of ethnobotanical plants used to treat bites and envenomations

Traditional herbalists and therapists, including 9 women and 16 men, making a total of 25 people, took part in the ethnobotanical survey for the inventory of plants used to treat snake bites and envenomations in the Bofidji - Ouest study area. The data obtained made it possible to calculate the relative frequencies for each plant, as well as their ethnobotanical use value. Listed below are the various plants, along with their scientific and vernacular names, families, orders, habitats and ethnobotanical use values. These plants are listed in simple Table 1 below.

Table 1 : Ethnobotanical plants treating bites and venoms

N°	Scientific name	Vernacular names	Families	Organ used	Relative citation			
					Number of quotation (n)	FRC calculated	∑ Si	UV
01	<i>Aframomum citratum</i> (J.Pereira) K.Schum.	Mondongo	Zingiberaceae	Fruit and leaf	25	01	55	02.20
02	<i>Agerantum conyzoïdes</i> L..	Ngwaka : Tangbabu, Dagbabu / Libinza : Ngele / Lomongo : Bokatola / Lokonda : Emanda, Lutu lo ntaba / Lonkundo : Likotsi / Budja : Ekbulu / Makutu : Mobondo	Asteraceae	Stem and leaf	25	01	68	02.72
03	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	Ndembu	Liliaceae	Leaf	15	0.60	42	01.68
04	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Aloevera		Leaf	13	0.52	29	01.16
05	<i>Alostonia congensis</i> Engl.	Mokuka (bokuka) / Ngwaka : Denga / Mbanza : Dungunikwa / Kitembo : Mukuka Lomongo : Bokuka	Apocynaceae	Leaf	22	0.88	63	02.52
06	<i>Amaranthus sp</i>	Bompoko o ngola	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	19	0.76	41	01.64
07	<i>Barteria fistulosa</i> (Mast.) Sleumer.	Bonkokombi (linkokombi) / Ngwaka : Kokombo / Mbanza : Augbekimue / Ngombe : Likokombo / Kisengele : Bonkomo nkomo Lomongo : Bonkonkomo	Passifloraceae	Leaves, bark, root	24	0.96	65	02.60
08	<i>Capsicum annuum</i> L.	Ngbendu (pilipili) / Mono : Djengele / Lingala : Pilipili / Ngwaka : Tandala / Kuala : Lolo gbendu	Solanaceae	Fruit and leaf	14	0.56	36	01.44
09	<i>Cercestis congensis</i> ENGL	Bololo	Araceae	Leaf	21	0.84	54	02.16
10	<i>Citrus acida</i> Pers.	Ndimu ngai	Rutaceae	Fruit, root	20	0.80	55	02.20
11	<i>Coelocaryon preussi</i> Warb.	Bosaka (ebondo)	Myristicaceae	Ecorce	24	0.96	66	02.64
12	<i>Cola acuminata</i> (P.Beauv.) Schott & Endl.	Likasu	Sterculiaceae	Fruit and root	19	0.76	45	01.80
13	<i>Costus podocephalus</i> Donn.Sm.	Musaso	Zingiberaceae	Leaf, fruit Stem and flower	23	0.92	59	02.16
14	<i>Costus afer</i> Gawl	Lingala : Monyeza (Bekako) / Lonkundo : Bansanga / Kirega : Malenge mabasumbu Ngwaka : Kanga / Kintandu :	Zingiberaceae	Leaf, fruit Stem and flower	22	0.88	60	02.40

		Munkeni Ngombe : Ngala kulu						
15	<i>Costus lucanusianus</i> J.Braun & K.Schum.	Lingala : Ngakulu	Zingiberaceae	Stem, leaf and flowers	21	0.84	59	02.36
16	<i>Cyrtosperma senegalense</i> (Schott) Engl.	Mantolo	Araceae	Leaf and rhizome	09	0.36	20	0.80
17	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i> Jacq.	Limbila	Aracaceae	Nuts and spongy matter on twigs	14	0.56	28	01.12
18	<i>Eleusina indica</i> (L.) Gaertn	Mpama : Lolongi lo mwelé / Lokonda : Ekoko / Ngwaka : Ndumulu / Kintandu : Kimbansi / Kitembo : Elulu / Libinza : Bakata / Lomongo : Likalabandja Kirega : Ibangubangu	Poaceae	Whole plant	24	0.96	62	02.48
19	<i>Erythrophleum suaveolens</i> (Guill. & Perr.) Brenan	Mbondo bololo (efomi)	Fabaceae	Leaf, bark and root	22	0.88	57	02.28
20	<i>Garcinia kola</i> Heckel	Museno (Ngadiadia)	Clusiaceae	Fruit	23	0.92	63	02.52
21	<i>Gnetum africanum</i> Welw.	Fumbwa (koko)	Gnetaceae	Leaf and stem	16	0.64	38	01.52
22	<i>Hymenocardia acida</i> Tul.	Ngaingai ya zamba	Malvaceae	Leaf, stem	24	0.96	60	02.40
23	<i>Mitragyna stipulosa</i> (DC.) Kuntze	Molulu	Rubiaceae	Fruit and leaf	25	01	69	02.76
24	<i>Morinda morindoides</i> (Baker) Milne-Redh.	Ngwaka : Gbozokanga, Buezokongo Ngbandi : Ngonzo konga / Lingala : Kongo bololo / Lokonda : Kongo bololo / Libinza : Kongo bololo / Lonkundo : Kong'ololo Mpama : Ngonga bololo	Rubiaceae	Leaves and stem	25	01	65	02.60
25	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.	Likula : Liloso	Fabaceae	Leaf, fruit and root	23	0.92	61	02.44
26	<i>Musa sp</i>	Likemba	Musaceae	Dry fruit and leaf and dry trunk	21	0.84	54	02.16
27	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Lingala : Lumbalumba / Mono : Anerakola / Kirega : Basenye / Lomongo : Bonsonsole / Bobangi : Nzangasani / Mpama : Monzangasano, Ososolo / Kisengele : Bonsonsolo / Kinunu : Nganga nsali / Tshiluba : Lueny	Lamiaceae	Leaf and stem	25	01	64	02.56

28	<i>Palisota schweinfurthii</i> C.B.Clarke	Libinza : Litetele : Ngwaka : Zazu, Kpato, Zâzo	Commelinaceae	Leaf, stem	25	01	69	02.76
29	<i>Canavalia ensiformis</i> (L.) DC.	Liwa za ndjo	Fabaceae		24	0.96	72	02.88
30	<i>Piptadeniastrum africanum</i> (Hook.f.) Brenan	Mokungu (bokungu) / Lomongo : Bokungu Ngbandi : Kungu / Ngwaka : Mokungu Lokonda : Bokungu / Mpama : Okungu	Mimosaceae	Fruit and leaf	25	01	70	02.80
31	<i>Quassia africana</i> (Baill.) Baill.	Lomongo : Yayotomba / Lonkundo : Yola yotomba / Lingala : Ekbetema / Mbole : Ekbetema	Simarubaceae	Bark and root	24	0.96	67	02.68
32	<i>Sansevieria liberica</i> Gérôme & Labroy	Lomongo : Fulele ya lokoto Nom vulgaire : Sansevière	Dracaenaceae	Root, leaf and bark of stem	22	0.88	60	02.40
33	<i>Sansevieria trifasciata</i> Prain	Ngwaka : Ndama, Gbua, Kuwa, Pua Libinza : Lilanga lankoi Nom vulgaire : Sansevière	Dracaenaceae	Leaf	21	0.84	61	02.44
34	<i>Scorodophloeus zenkeri</i> Harms	Bofizi (bopizi) / Lomongo : Bofili / Lokonda : Bopili / Mpama : Mbopili	Caesalpiniaceae	Leaf	19	0.76	58	02.32
35	<i>Smilax anceps</i> Willd.	Likokoloko (Walokodjwa) / Kirega : Musulindi / Lomongo : Bokiki	Smilacaceae	Leaf and bark	24	0.96	69	02.76
36	<i>Thomandersia hensii</i> De Wild. & T.Durrand	Monkooka Ngwaka : Ngboka / Mokula : Mangbanda / Mbanza : Ngoka / Lomongo : Imele mpaka	Ancathaceae	Leaf	25	01	70	02.80
37	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	Tangawisi	Zingiberaceae	Leaves and stem.	25	01	66	02.64

Interpretation of the Data simple table 1 : The inventory resulted in 37 plant species, all identified. The other 38 species are divided into 27 families including Zingiberaceae which is represented with 05 species (*Fromomum citratum*, *Costus polycephalus*, *Costus afer*, *Costus lucanusianus* and *Zingiber officinalis*). The family of Fabaceae follows with 2 species (*Erythrophloeun suaveolens* and *Mucuna pruriens*), the family of Dracaenaceae with 2 species (*Sansevieria liberica* and *Sansevieria trifasciata*), the family of Araceae (), the family of Rubiaceae with 2 species (*Mitragyne stipilosa* and *Morinda morindoides*) and the Araceae family with 2 species (*Certis congensis* and *Cystoperma senegalense*). The remains of families are usually represented with a species. There are 3 species with a VU below 1.50 (*Aloe vera*, *Capsicum annaum*, *Elaeis guineensis*), one species also has a slightly above average VU (*Gnetum africanum*, VU = 01.52). This implies that other species have a high ethnobotanical use value and are either overexploited or endangered. It may be a progressive degradation linked to their natural environment, given the increasing population pressure due mainly to the high presence of non-native species and also to habitat degradation due to the logging of community forests in Bofidji – West. Plants with high VU may be the most commonly used and preferred because of their availability or perceived effectiveness. These usage frequencies could also reflect traditional knowledge and

confidence in natural remedies. These plants could also finally be the most accessible of the low-value ones. Accessibility to these plants is a key factor in their use. Readily available plants are probably the ones used, although other plants may be more effective but less available.

06. Graph associated with data table 6 : Differences in specific knowledge between traditional practitioners and female health practitioners

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 6 : Men and women may specialize in different aspects of traditional medicine. For example, some men may be more versed in treatments for specific ailments such as sports injuries, while some women may specialize in care related to maternity and reproductive health. The gender involved in the treatment of bites and envenomations, certainly of different ethnicities, may have specific knowledge, hence the existence of both gender-specific plants in equally distinct traditional medicinal practices and preparations. These differences in plant use between traditional healers and practitioners, or between groups and associations of traditional healers and practitioners, or between ethnic groups of traditional healers and practitioners, could indicate variations in the ethnobiological knowledge used against snake bites and envenomations, but always under environmental influences and cultural traditions.

07. Graph associated with data table 7 : Differences in treatment methods using plant diversity

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 7 : There may be variations in the specific methods used to treat certain conditions. For example, male traditional practitioners may prefer to use

certain herbs or ritual practices in the treatment of certain illnesses, while women may use other medicinal plants or healing techniques. The use of different plant extracts would testify to appropriate knowledge and also to a diversity of operating modes, but also to varied modes of preparation depending on the use made of each part of the plant, or the association of extracts collected from different plants, or even different feet depending on the guidance that traditional practitioners might receive after diagnosis assisted by invisible beings.

The different extracts presuppose the presence of molecules with different therapeutic activities at different intensities. According to the data in the table, leaves, roots, stems, bark, root barks and branches are the most popular and common uses, while sap, bulbs, inflorescences, rhizomes, rachis, pods, seeds and others not mentioned in the work would constitute specific extracts, generally of little use to traditional and traditional practitioners, with the exception of pods and bulbs. The differences observed would justify the differences in the methods used by some and others specifically to combat snake bites and envenomations.

09. Graph associated with data table 8 : Differences in treatment methods using animal diversity

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 8 : There may be variations in the specific methods used to treat certain conditions. For example, male traditional healers may prefer the use of certain animal parts or ritual practices in the treatment of certain illnesses, while female traditional healers may use other medicinal animal parts or healing techniques. The results suggest that male and female traditional practitioners have slightly different approaches to the use of animal resources. This could be due to differences in culture, access to resources, or perceived effectiveness of treatments. Traditional practitioners seem to favor certain specific extracts (hair, liver, fat, eggs, bile, venom) for which they seem to have a particular confidence or specialization. Traditional practitioners, on the other hand, show a more diversified use, which may reflect a more experimentalist or adaptive approach. The table reveals a varied and sometimes distinct use of animal extracts between male and female tradipraticians. While women show a marked specialization for certain extracts, men adopt a more

diversified approach. These observations are important for understanding the dynamics of traditional practices, and could have implications for wildlife management and health policy formulation.

10. Graph associated with data table 9 : Differences in treatment methods using plant extracts in combination with animal extracts

Interpretation of graph associated with data table 9 : There may be differences in the specific methods used to treat certain conditions. For example, male traditional healers may favour the use of certain animal parts or ritual practices in the treatment of certain diseases, while women may use different medicinal animal parts or healing techniques. This table shows the combined use of plant and animal extracts (vertebrate, invertebrate, fish) in the treatment of snake bites and envenomations by male and female traditional healers in Groupement Bofidji Ouest, DRC. The table highlights the gender differences in the combination of plant and animal extracts. Female and male traditional healers show a different use of associations between plant and animal extracts. However, certain associations seem to be more common in one gender than the other. For example, female traditional healers show a high use of plant associations with vertebrate, invertebrate, bone, animal skin and boa bile extracts (100%), indicating a preference or specialisation in these combinations.

Traditional practitioners also make extensive use of plant associations with vertebrates, invertebrates, fats, animal skulls and mineral extracts, with usage rates of 100%. The most common associations among traditional practitioners are plant extracts with vertebrates, invertebrates, bones and animal skins, all of which are used at 100%. Fish extracts and plant associations with boa urine and bile are also commonly used (77%). This shows a high degree of homogeneity in the practices of traditional practitioners with regard to certain specific associations. Among traditional practitioners, associations between plants and extracts of vertebrates, invertebrates, fats, animal skulls and mineral extracts are universally used (100%). However, their use of combinations with bones (56.25%) and animal skin (50%) is much less frequent than that of traditional healers.

It should also be noted that plant associations with urine are completely absent among traditional healers, whereas they are used by 77% of traditional healers. In terms of specific preferences, we note the existence of common associations: Associations of plants with vertebrates, invertebrates, fats, skulls, mineral extracts, honey, aromatics, scales and palm kernel oil are practices shared by both sexes at high rates (100% for most). In terms of "Marked differences", female traditional practitioners make

greater use of associations with urine, animal skin and boa bile, which may be related to specific beliefs or knowledge transmitted within female communities, while male traditional practitioners show a notable absence of urine use in their treatments, which may reflect different cultural preferences or practices. In terms of "implications for traditional practices", these gender differences may indicate a distinct specialisation of medical practices between men and women, each bringing a unique expertise to local traditional medicine. The diversity of associations between plant and animal extracts shows a complexity in treatments, suggesting in-depth knowledge and know-how acquired about the complementary properties of plants and animals. The results may also reflect the adaptation of practices to available resources or the transmission of knowledge specific to each genus.

11. Graph associated with data table 10 : Differences in cultural and ritual approach

Interpretation of the *Graph associated with data table 10* : Male and female traditional healers may have different approaches based on specific rituals, incantations or ceremonies associated with their healing practices. This table presents the different cultural and ritual approaches adopted by male and female traditional healers in the Groupement Bofidji Ouest, DRC, as part of their traditional practices. It highlights gender-specific practices in terms of rituals, incantations, initiations, and other cultural and spiritual elements. Concerning participation in ritual practices by gender : Both genders participate widely in cultural and ritual practices, with some notable variations. Tradipraticians are 100% involved in the majority of practices, including rituals, incantations, bathing, sacred forest sojourns, contact with sacred objects, passage between the feet, threading, solemn declarations, enthronement, and cash/pledge redemptions. This shows a very uniform participation and importance given to these practices in their approach. Tradipraticians also share a high level of participation in these practices, but there are significant variations in initiation and sacred forest sojourns, where 75% and 50% respectively are involved. With regard to "Gender comparison" : Tradipraticians have 100% participation in most cultural and ritual approaches, indicating the importance given to these practices in their treatments and transmission of knowledge. Practices such as incantations, nocturnal rituals, contact with sacred objects and enthronements are universally adopted, perhaps reflecting a more accentuated spiritual dimension in their practices.

Tradipraticians are also very active in ritual practices, but show greater variability in certain activities. For example, initiation and sojourns in the sacred forest are less frequent among them (75% and 50% respectively), which could indicate a difference in beliefs or access to these practices. The practices of fire-burning, enthronement and cash/bequest redemption are universally adopted (100%), suggesting that these rituals play a crucial role in their treatment and in the recognition of their status in the community. With regard to "Specific preferences and differences": Night ceremonies and bathing are adopted by both genders, but with a slight difference in the involvement of traditional practitioners, where only 56.25% participate in these practices. Staying in the sacred forest is more common among female tradipraticians (100%) than male tradipraticians (50%), which may reflect differences in access or role in traditional society.

Initiations : Although very common, they are not universal among traditional practitioners (75%), whereas they are practiced by 100% of female practitioners, perhaps highlighting a stricter requirement or a more deeply-rooted tradition among women. On "Cultural implications": Ritual and cultural practices seem to be integrally linked to traditional treatments, with marked gender differences. This could be linked to distinct roles within the community, with perhaps different expectations for men and women in terms of participation in rituals. These differences in commitment to certain practices could reflect cultural specializations or traditions that are transmitted differently by gender. The table reveals that cultural and ritual approaches are deeply rooted in male and female tradipraticians' practices, with high participation in the majority of rituals. However, some practices show gender differences in participation, which could indicate distinct cultural roles or variations in the interpretation of ritual practices. These results underline the importance of cultural and spiritual dimensions in traditional healing practices and knowledge transmission.

12. Graph associated with data table 11 : The different channels for acquiring traditional knowledge according to the non-tradipratician sample

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 11 : This table shows the percentage trends in the different channels of knowledge acquisition by the non-tradipratician sample who took part in the surveys. Inheritance is the predominant channel, followed by initiation, which is often a totally ritualized process. The percentage allocated to self-learning would unequivocally demonstrate the share of non-

tradition, which sees itself as a new current manipulated by infiltrators. This is in fact a desecration of endogenous knowledge and practices.

Utilisation de R

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

p-value = 0.858

The P-value (= 0.8598) is less or greater than 0.005, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant association between seasons and sex of bitten persons.

13. Graph associated with data table 11 : The different diagnostic methods revealed by the sample of non-tradipraticians

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 12 : The traditional laboratory appears to be the most widely used means of diagnosis (44.25%) among traditional practitioners, as seen by patients and those who have experienced the condition. There is some use of modern medicine by traditional practitioners, in particular laboratory tests (13.27% and 06.19% use clinical expertise from modern doctors), which opens the door to integration of certain advantages offered by modern medicine, as well as to collaboration between practitioners of the two medicines for the benefit of the patient. Other traditional means of diagnosis are oracles by revealing spirits, and sometimes even by patients themselves.

13. Graph associated with data table 12 : Gender-differentiated positive socio-cultural perspectives

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 12 : The traditional laboratory appears to be the most widely used means of diagnosis (44.25%) among traditional practitioners, as seen by patients and those who have experienced the condition. There is some use of modern medicine by traditional practitioners, in particular laboratory tests (13.27% and 06.19% use clinical expertise from modern doctors), which opens the door to integration of certain advantages offered by modern medicine, as well as to collaboration between practitioners of the two medicines for the benefit of the patient. Other traditional means of diagnosis are oracles by revealing spirits, and sometimes even by patients themselves.

14. Graph associated with data table 13 : Perspectives on the integration of traditional medicine into modern snakebite treatment protocols in Bofidji - West.

Interpretation of the Graph associated with data table 13 : 33.33% of female traditional practitioners rated this collaboration as “good”, “fairly good” or “non-existent”. Among traditional practitioners, responses were more varied : 21.05% rated collaboration as “good”, 26.31% as “fairly good”, and 36.84% as “non-existent”. Overall, 28% of practitioners rate this collaboration as “good”, 32% as “fairly good” and 40% as “non-existent”. It seems that, despite some collaborative efforts, a significant proportion of traditional practitioners consider that there is no real collaboration with modern health structures. 44.44% of traditional practitioners accept this idea, against 55.55% who reject it. Only 15.79% are open to it, while 47.37% are strongly opposed and 10.53% don't think it's important. There is a majority reluctance, particularly among traditional practitioners, to condition their treatments on medical laboratory tests, probably due to mistrust of modern medical practices. A higher proportion of female traditional practitioners (66.66%) are in favor of this collaboration, while 22.22% find it “non-existent”. The perception of traditional practitioners is more divided : 31.58% consider this collaboration “good” and 42.10% “non-existent”. Female traditional practitioners seem more open to collaboration with academic and international institutions than male traditional practitioners. 66.66% of female traditional practitioners rated this collaboration as “good”, compared with 31.58% of male traditional practitioners. The proportion of those who consider this collaboration “non-existent” is higher among

traditional practitioners (42.10%). There seems to be a greater willingness among women to work with other traditional healers in the field of CAM.

Conclusion

Retrospective surveys carried out in the Bofidji - West grouping, Bikoro Territory, Equateur Province, revealed the various ethnobiological resources used in the treatment of snakebites and envenomations in this rural environment, where the population is characterised by its vulnerability to both of these diseases. These surveys revealed the existence of around thirty plant species used in ethnobotany, but some of these plants are used either alone, others in association with each other, or in association with certain animal resources. This is a wide range of medicinal plants used by local traditional healers, and the ways in which they are used reveal certain particularities from a gender point of view, but these differences are not statistically significant.

The state of play revealed by the different Use Values (UV) stigmatises a growing threat to the ecological future of this wealth. These ethnobotanical values show that these species have great therapeutic value, but from an ecological point of view, they are in danger of extinction. The study provided important information on the use of resources by traditional practitioners. This is the case for the combination of plant extracts with animal extracts. Many local traditional practitioners stated that the best traditional medicines for immunising against snakebites and for treating snakebites and envenomations are drawn from phytozootherapies. Snakes are an important part of this combination. These aspects have been documented and could form the next stage of our publications.

The study identified a number of barriers and challenges to integrating traditional snakebite and envenomation practices in rural areas of the Bofidji - West group into modern medical structures, in order to maximise patients' chances of recovery. We know that the methods used by traditional medicine are not without danger. Analysing the various obstacles faced by the community in accessing improved traditional treatments alongside modern envenomation treatments, and exploring the possible complementarities between Bofidji - West tradipraticians and tradipraticians on the one hand, and the complexity of relations between tradipraticians and tradipraticians vis-à-vis modern health providers on the other, would be a prelude to respectful cooperation between the two forms of medicine.

References

1. Amui, SF., Puga, R.D., Soares, AM., Giuliatti, S., 2011. Plant-antivenom : database of anti-venom medicinal plants. *Electron. J. Biotechnol.* 14(1) 6-7.
2. Ateazing, A.G, Fotso, L.P., Tchotsoua, M., Cardon, A., 2009. Modelling a massive multi-agent decision-support system in traditional medicine pp 1-12. <https://hal.science/tel-01842116v5>
3. Ateazing, G.A., Pavón, J., 2008. An Ontology for African Traditional Medicine. Springer. pp 329 - 337. DOI:[10.1007/978-3-540-85863-8_39](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-85863-8_39)
4. ATIBT., 2006. Summary of Equatorial Forests-Wildlife Component. Ed. ATIBT.
5. Aubert, M., De Haro, L., Jouglard, J., 1996. Les envenimations par les serpents exotiques [Envenomation by exotic snakes]. *Med Trop (Mars)*. 56(4): 384-92. French. PMID: 9139199.

6. Ayékotchami, J.D., Adandé, B.F., 2021. "Use of medicinal plants to prevent and cure snake bites: status and outlook (bibliographical summary) ". BASE. 25 (2): 57-70. DOI: 10.25518/1780-4507.18915
7. Ayimdji, A., Koussoube, S., Fotso, L.P., Balira, K.O. (2012). Using Methontology to Build a Deep Ontology for African Traditional Medicine, First Steps. ARIMA PP1-12, 2012. DOI:[10.4236/iim.2011.36030](https://doi.org/10.4236/iim.2011.36030)
8. Baader, F., Hollunder, B., 1991. Terminological Knowledge Representation System with Complete Inference Algorithms. First International Workshop on Processing Declarative Knowledge. pp 67-86.
9. Balagizi, I.K., 2010. Traditional medicine and modern medicine need cooperation, 48 p
10. Barma, A.D., Mohanty, P.J., Bhuyan, R.N., 2014. A review on anti-venom activity of some medicinal plants. Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res. 5(5), 1612-1615.
11. Bayeli, I.G., Joiris, V., Lohandjola, N.G., Habari, J-P., 2019. Contribution to the study of medicinal plants used in the treatment of abscesses in the territory of Bikoro, Equateur province in DRC. Int. J. Biol. Chem. Sci. 13(1) : 353-368. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v13i1.28>
12. Bellefleur, J.P., Le Dantec, P., 2005. Prise en charge hospitalière des morsures de serpent en Afrique [Hospital care of snakebites in Africa]. Bull Soc Pathol Exot. 98(4): 273-6. French. PMID: 16402573.
13. Boika Monzoi Ndinga, Victor Pwema Kiamfu, Willy Lusasi Swana, Dieudonné Musibono, Seraphin Ifuta Ndey (2021): Ichthyological diversity of the flooded swamp forest of the Lake Tumba hydrographic network on the Mbandaka - CREF Mabali road axis in the Bikoro territory, province of Equateur (DRC), IJPSAT, pp 156 - 168. Recherche ID: J - 1399-2016 DOI: 10.52155
14. Camou-Guerrero A., Reyes-Garcia, V., Martinez-Ramos, M., Casas, A. 2022. Knowledge and use value of plant species in a raramuri community : a gender perspective for conservation. Human Ecology. 2008; 36: 259-272. Open Access Research Journal of Life Sciences. 04(01), 001–010
15. Chabrier, J.Y., 2010. Medicinal plants and forms of use in phytotherapy, Thesis in Pharmacology-Odontology, Henri Poincare University - Nancy 1.
16. Carillon, A., 2009. Place of phytotherapy in health systems in the 21st century ; SIPAM Conference -Djerba March 2009; pp 1-7.
17. Chippaux, J.P., 1998. Snake-bites: appraisal of a global situation. Bull. WHO. 76(5), 515-524.
18. Chippaux, J.P., Vieillefosse, S., Sall, O., Mafouta, R., Diallo, A., 2005. Evaluation of the incidence of snakebites in Senegal. Bull Soc Pathol Ex. 98(4): 277-282.
19. Diarra, A., 2005. Epidemiological, clinical and therapeutic aspects of snake bites in national hospitals in Mali ; 10-year retrospective study. Medical thesis. DOI: [10.1007/s13149-012-0239-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13149-012-0239-8)

20. Dramé, B.S. (2000). The snake bite poisoning accidents in the surgical emergency department of the Gabriel Touré hospital. Thesis Med, Bamako, No. 120. <https://www.bibliosante.ml/handle/123456789/7398>
21. El Hattimyr, M.F., 2013. Snakebites : Données du Centre Anti Poison et de Pharmacovigilance du Maroc 2009 à 2013. Toxicologie, Maroc N° 24 - 1er trimestre. Doi: 10.1007/s13149-012-0240-2.
22. Falçal, El H., Chafiq, F., Abdelmajid, S., Rachida, S.B., 2021. Ophidian enomations in children in Morocco : epidemiological aspects, and risk factors, Research. E3S Web of Conferences 319 (1):01071. DOI: <http://dx.Doi.org/10.13070/rs.fr.3.1513>
23. Félix-Silva, J., Silva-Junior, A.A., Zucolotto, S.M., Fernandes-Pedrosa, MF., 2017. Medicinal Plants for the Treatment of Local Tissue Damage Induced by Snake Venoms: An Overview from Traditional Use to Pharmacological Evidence. Evid Based Complement Alternat Med. 2017: 5748256. Doi: 10.1155/2017/5748256.
24. Fourn, L., Adè, G., Fayomi, E.B., Zohoun, T., 2005. Aspects épidémiologiques des morsures de serpent au Bénin [Epidemiological aspects of snakebites in Benin]. Bull Soc Pathol Exot. 98(4):291-2. French. PMID: 16402578.
25. Gentilini, M., 1993. Venomous animals. Flammarion Médecine science, fifth edition, Paris 715-721. 682 p.
26. Gomes, A., Das, R., Sarkhel, S., Mishra, R., Mukherjee, S., Bhattacharya, S., Gomes, A., 2010. Herbs and herbal constituents active against snake bite. Indian J. Exp. Biol. 48(9) : 865-78. PMID : 21506494.
27. Inkoto, C.L., Ngbolua, K.N., Kilembe, J.T., Masengo, C.A., Lukoki, F.L., Tshilanda, D.D., Tshibangu, D.S-T., Mpiana, P.T., 2021b. A Mini Review on the Phytochemistry and Products Pharmacology of *Aframomum alboviolaceum* (Zingiberaceae). South Asian Research Journal of Natural. 4(3): 24-35. DOI:[10.53771/ijlsra.2021.1.2.0069](https://doi.org/10.53771/ijlsra.2021.1.2.0069)
28. Inkoto, L.C., Ngbolua, K.N., Bokungu, E.P., Masengo, A.C., Iteku, B.J., Tshilanda, D.D., Tshibangu, T.S.D. & Mpiana, T.P. (2021a). Phytochemistry and Pharmacology of *Aframomum angustifolium* (Sonn.) K. Schum (Zingiberaceae), South Asian Research Journal of Natural Products 5(1): 21-36. <http://ebooks.keeplibrary.com/id/eprint/17>
29. Kabena, K.O., Ngombe, K.N., Ngbolua, K.N., Kikufi, B.A., Lassa, L, Mboloko, E.J., Mpiana, P.T., Lukoki, L.F., 2014. Ethnobotanical and ecological studies of feminine intimate hygiene plants used in Kinshasa (Democratic Republic of Congo). International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences 8 (6) : 2626-2642.
30. Kassogue, A., 2006. Renal complications of venomation by snake bite at the SUC HGT from January to December 2004, Thesis University of Bamako, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy.
31. Konda K.M. et al. 2011. Medicinal plants of transitions, Province of Equateur DRC, publisher Paul Lathan, 418 Pages. ISBN - 10 0955420857 ISBN - 13 978-0955420856
32. Kouame, A., 2018. Traditional medicine management system in a social and semantic web platform : a visual ontology-based approach. Artificial intelligence [cs.AI]. Thesis, Université Gaston Berger de Saint-Louis (Senegal). Hal-03160145, [version 1](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-03160145) (13-03-202).

33. Lougbegnono, T., Nassi, K.M., Gbessog, H.F., 2015. Ethnobotanique quantitative de l'usage de *Chrysophyllum albidum* G. Don par les populations locales au Bénin. Journal of Applied Biosciences. 95 : 9028 – 9038 ISSN 1997–5902. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/jab.v95i1.12>
34. Masengo, C.A., Lengbiye, E.M., Inkoto, C.L., Gbolo, B.Z., Tshilanda, D.D., Tshibangu, D.S.-T., Baholy, R.R., Guy, I.B., Ngbolua KN, Mpiana PT, Mudogo V., 2021. Literature Review on the Phytochemistry and Pharmaco-Biological, Nutritional and Cosmetic Properties of *Lippia multiflora* and New Research Perspectives. South Asian Research Journal of Natural Products. 4(4):35-48.
35. Masunda, A.T., Inkoto, C.L., Bongo, G.N., Oleko, Wa Oloko J.D., Ngbolua, K.N., Tshibangu, D.S.T., Tshilanda, D.D., Mpiana, P.T., 2019. Ethnobotanical and Ecological Studies of Plants Used in the Treatment of Diabetes in Kwango, Kongo Central and Kinshasa in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. International Journal of Diabetes and Endocrinology. 4(1): 18-25. Doi: 10.11648/j.ijde.20190401.14.
36. Mokekola, EB., Ngbolua, K.N., Idrissa, A.Z., Bayeli, G.I., Mulonda, A.B., Mawunu, M., Gires, E.M., 2024a. Incidence of snakebites in the area between Mbandaka and Motongambale in the commune of Mbandaka (Equateur Province), Democratic Republic of the Congo. Orapuh Journal. 5(1), e1105. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/orapj.v5i1.5>
37. Mokekola, B.E., Ngbolua, K.N., Zabo, A.I., Ilumbe, G.B., Mulonda, A.B., Mawunu, M., Engomba, G.M., Masengo, C.A., Bokulu, A., 2024b. Incidence and traditional management of snakebites in the Bofidji-Bolenge Grouping, Wangata Commune, Mbandaka City, Democratic Republic of the Congo. *Orapuh Journal*, 5(4), e1133. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/orapj.v5i4.33>
38. Mokekola, E.B., Idrissa, Z.A., Chifundera, K.Z., Ndombe, T.R., Mwange, K.R., Mukeba, B.F., 2022b. Evaluation of snakebites and their treatment in the Bonginda/Bikoro DR Congo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2022.10.1.0058>
39. Mokekola, E.B., Idrissa, Z.A., Ndombe, T.R., Mukeba, B.F., Mulonda, B.A., Muanda, N.F., Mangambu, M.JD, Chifundera, K.Z., Chakupewa, F.M., 2022c. Endogenous knowledge of traditional healers on plants used against hepatitis in Mbandaka/DR Congo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53022/oarjls.2022.4.1.0049>
40. Mokekola, E.B., Ndombe, T.R., Mwange, K.R., Mulonda, B.A., Mukeba, B.F., Chifundera, K.Z. & Idrissa, Z.A., 2022a. Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants against ophidian envenomations in the Bonginda/Bikoro Group in DR Congo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53346/wjapls.2022.2.2.0024>
41. Ngbolua, K.N., Mihigo, S.O., Liyongo, C.L., Masengo, C.A., Tshibangu, D.T., Zoawe, B.G., Baholy, R., Fatiany, R.P., Mpiana, T.P., 2016. Ethno-botanical survey of plant species used in traditional medicine in Kinshasa city (Democratic Republic of the Congo). Tropical Plant Research. 3(2) : 413-427.
42. Ngbolua, K.N., Inkoto, C.L., Mongo, N.L., Ashande, C.M., Masens, Y.B., Mpiana, P.T. 2019. Ethnobotanical and floristic study of some medicinal plants marketed in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo Rev. Mar. Sci. Agron. Vet. 7 (1): 118-128

43. Ngbolua, KN., Nagahuedi, S.M.J., Ashande, M.C., Djoza, D.R., Mpiana, T.P., Virima, M. (2021). Bibliographic synthesis on snakes and medicinal plants used in traditional medicine against ophidian envenomations. *Int J Appl Res* 7(4) : 305-314. DOI:10.22271/allresearch.2021.v7.i4e.8510.
44. Ngene, J.-P., Ngoule, C.C., Pouka, K.C.-M., Mvogo, Ottou, P.B., Ndjib, R.C., Dibong, S.D., & Mpondo, M.E. (2015). Importance dans la pharmacopée traditionnelle des plantes à flavonoïdes vendues dans les marchés de Douala est (Cameroun), p.8194-8210. DOI:10.4314/jab.v88i1.6
45. Ngunde ST-N, Inkoto CL, Kowozogono RK, Zua TG, Mayundo BK, Iteku JB. (2021). Ethnobotanical study of plants used in traditional medicine in Gini (Yakoma, NordUbangi, Democratic Republic of Congo). *International Journal of Applied Research* 7(1) : 36-43.
46. Pagezy H. (2006). Le contexte magico-religieux de la pêche au lac Tumba ; « entre le normal » et l'insolite, *journal des Africanistes* 76 (2) : 44-62.
47. Soares, A.M., Ticli, F.K., Marcussi, S., Lourenço, M.V., Januário, A.H., Sampaio, S.V., Giglio, J.R., Lomonte, B., Pereira, P.S. (2005). Medicinal plants with inhibitory properties against snake venoms. *Curr Med Chem.* 12(22) : 2625-41. Doi:10.2174/092986705774370655
48. Sowa F. (2013) : Relations of power and domination in a world polity: The politics of indigeneity and national identity greenland
49. Tardío, J., Pardo-de-Santayana, M. 2008. Cultural Importance Indices : A Comparative Analysis Based on the Useful Wild Plants of Southern Cantabria (Northern Spain). *Economic Botany.* 62(1): 24-39.
50. UNDP (2009): Province of Equateur DRC: Poverty and living conditions of households
51. United Nations. (1992). Convention on biological diversity. Retrieved from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/legal/cbd-en.pdf>
52. Upasani, S.V., Beldar, V.G., Tatiya, A.U., Upasani, M.S., Surana, S.J., & Patil, D.S. (2017). Ethnomedicinal plants used for snakebite in India : a brief overview. *Integr Med Res.* 6(2):114-130. Doi: 10.1016/j.imr.2017.03.001.
53. World Medical Association, 2013. World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA.* 310(20), 2191–2194. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.281053>